

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND ALKYLATION REACTION OF PHENOLS WITH THE PARTICIPATION OF ZEOLITE CATALYSTS

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ABSTRACT

Individual isomers of ethylphenol and mixtures of isomers occupy a special place among alkylphenols. They are used in the production of pesticides, resins, plasticizers, stabilizers, dyes, aromatic substances, polymer materials with various properties, etc. They are considered important products and semi-products of small and large tonnage organic synthesis. In recent years, further diversification of application areas has increased industrial demand for them.

Keywords: Phenol, cresol, ethanol, catalyst, nickel, palladium.

A convenient method for obtaining alkyl derivatives of phenols is their catalytic alkylation reaction with alcohols. Optimum catalysts for gas-phase ethylation of phenols are developed and the process is controlled, becoming relevant in terms of its occurrence characteristics and regularities, allowing for the expansion and systematic collection of scientific knowledge.

In the presence of pentasil-type zeolites and their modified samples, catalysts with active selective and stable use properties for ethylation reactions of phenol and cresols, processing of Y, HM was carried out to obtain individual isomers of ethylphenol and ethyl cresols.

First, studies were conducted to determine the effect of m catalyst content on the parameters of the alkylation reaction of phenol and 2-methyl phenol with ethanol. Artificial HMs with $v(x)$ 10, 18, 25, 45 in silica (IV) oxide aluminum (iii) oxide were obtained by exposing de-cationized NaM samples ($x = \text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 10$) to aluminum-free coating. The degree of crystallization of the obtained HM is 95% when $x=18$ and 90% when $x=45$.

Since the catalysts used in the alkylation reaction of phenol and 2-methylphenol with ethanol have low

stability, they are variously cationized. The stability of the catalysts obtained in the alkylation reaction of 2-methylphenol with ethanol is shown in Figure 1. Compared to HM, the 1.5 wt % NiHM catalyst works stably for 40 hours, while the 1.0 wt % PdHM catalyst works stably in alkylation. Response within 60 hours. On the other hand, the modification of HM catalyst with nickel and palladium has a great effect on the separation of 2-methyl monoethylphenol. For this purpose, the product yield increases from 19.1% (HM) to 32.1% (1.5% NiHM) and 38.0% (1.0 PdHM).

Modification of the HM catalyst with nickel and palladium gave a more effective result in the $x=18$ sample. Modification of silicon oxide HM with -25-45 to alumina has little effect on the properties of these catalysts in the alkylation reaction. Thus, while the conversion of 2-methylphenol in the alkylation reaction with NiHM ($x=25$) is 18%, this indicator is only 12.5% in NiHM ($x=45$). When the alkylation reaction of 2-methylphenol with ethanol is carried out in the presence of PdH mordenite ($x=25$), the initial conversion of phenol is 21.8%.

Figure 1

Work constant of sample m in the alkylation reaction of 2-methylphenol with ethanol

Reaction conditions t-3600c, v-0.5 (st-1), - 2-methylphenol: ethanol 1:1

HM (x=18); 2. 1.5% NiHM 3. 1.0% PdHM

The results of the study of the alkylation reaction of 2-methylphenol with ethanol in the presence of modified HM catalysts are given in table 1. The analysis of these results shows that NiHM and especially PdHM catalysts show more interesting properties in the alkylation reaction. In the synthesis of ethyl cresols, the activity of both catalysts increases significantly compared to the initial m. On the other hand, a significant change is observed in the isomer composition of the obtained 2-methyl monoethylphenol. In the monoethyl cresol

mixture formed in the presence of NiHM, the mass ratio of the o-isomer to the p-isomer is 1:0.9, and in the presence of the PdHM catalyst, this ratio is 0.83:1. In an anol-based mixture, 2-methyl-5-ethylphenol and other isomers, including small amounts of 2-methyl-3-ethylphenol, 2-methylphenol, and monoethylcresol, are practical for these isomers doesn't happen. The third catalyst used in the alkylation reaction - FeHM is of little importance compared to other systems.

With the participation of HM catalyst modified with nickel, palladium and iron

Results of the study of the alkylation reaction of 2-methylphenol with ethanol

Reaction condition: t-3600c, v--0.5 (st-1), -2-HOC6H4CH3: C2H5OH=1:1

Table 1

The name of the indicator	Catalyst composition, mass %		
	1,5 Ni; 98,5-HM (x=18)	1,0 Pd; 99,0 HM (x=18)	1,5 Fe; 99,0 HM (x=18)
Conversion, % 2-methylphenol of ethanol	37,0 81,5	42,2 82,7	17,2 90,1
Yield of products calculated based on converted 2-methyl number, % 2-methyl-monomethyl phenol 2-methyl diethyl phenols	86,1 8,5	90,0 5,7	78,8 7,0
Isomeric composition of 2-methyl-monoethylphenols, by mass%	50,8	40,5	90,5
2-ethyl-6-methylphenol	42,2	48,5	9,0
2-methyl-4 ethylphenol 2-methyl-3 ethylphenol	1,0	-	-
2-methyl-5 ethylphenol	6,0	1,0	0,5

Thus, the selectivity of the reaction with respect to 2-ethyl-6-methylphenol decreases from 58.1 to 40.5%. Although a further increase in palladium killing capacity (2.0%) improved the response parameters, this increase was less pronounced. In the alkylation reaction with the palladium-modified m catalyst, the conversion rates of the starting materials also increase significantly. Increasing the mass fraction of palladium in the catalyst from 0.1% to 1.0% increases the conversion of 2-methylphenol by 10% and reaches 42.2%. A further increase in m-killing of the modifier (2%) has little effect on the conversion of 2-methylphenol (44.8%).

When the mass fraction of palladium is 1.0%, it is assumed to be in small dispersion on the catalyst surface, and at higher kill rates, the modifier is assumed to be in large dispersion. The high dispersion of palladium in the selected PdHM catalyst allows adjusting the

acidic properties of the active centers of the catalytic system.

Then, the influence of palladium on the HM catalyst (x=18) on the parameters of the alkylation reaction of Ni 2-methylphenol with ethanol was studied and the obtained results are shown in figure 2.

Modification of HM with palladium has a significant effect on the alkylation reaction of 2-methylphenol with ethanol. At this time, the share of p-alkylation is constantly increasing compared to o-alkylation. When the mass fraction of palladium is 1.0%, p-alkylation is dominant and there is a selectivity of the reaction to 2-methyl-4-ethyl phenol in the mixture of 2-methylmonoethyl phenol and 2-methyl-4-ethyl phenol. 48.5%. Increasing the mass fraction of palladium from 0.1 to 1.0% also decreases the share of 2-methylphenol o-alkylation reaction.

Figure 2

2- modified in the alkylation reaction of methylphenol with ethanol

Steady state study of PdHM catalyst

Reaction conditions: $t=3600c$, $\square=0.5$ (st-1),

$N = 2-HOC_6H_4CH_3:C_2H_5oh = 1:1$

The concentration of ethanol in the initial mixture is 30% by mass

The viscosity of ethanol in the initial mixture is 17.6% by mass X

As can be seen from Table 2, the 2-methyl-monoethylphenol mixture obtained at $\leq 365C^0$ consists of 2-ethyl-6-methyl- and 2-methyl-4-ethylphenols. The inclusion of palladium in hm enables a significant increase in the mass share of the latter in the mixture of 2-methyl-6-ethyl and 2-methyl-4-ethyl phenols. Increasing T to $390C^0$ allows obtaining other isomers in the mixture of 2-methylmonoethylphenol. Complexation of the isomeric composition is also observed in the 2-methyl-diethylphenol mixture. A similar change in the composition of mono- and

diethyl-o-cresol isomers occurs when the contact time increases. The selectivity of the reaction against 2-methyl-6-methyl and 2-methyl-4-ethylphenols at a value of 0.3 (st-1) of the given raw material is also significantly reduced (table 2). the rate of isomerization and dismutation reactions of the obtained alkylphenols partially increases. In general, under the conditions chosen for the alkylation reaction of 2-methylphenol with ethanol in the presence of PdHM catalyst, the contribution of the above external transformations and other unnecessary reactions can be considered negligible.

The effect of t on the alkylation reaction of 2-methylphenol with ethanol

Reaction conditions: $\nu=0.5$ (st-1), $\nu=2$ -methylphenol : ethanol 1:1,

Consumption of hydrogen per 1 liter of raw material is 800 liters per hour

Table 2

The name of the indicator	T, °C			
	315	340	365	390
Received in mass % Including Ethanol	17,0	14,2	10,4	5,6
2-methylphenethyl	4,0	2,4	1,6	0,4
2-methylphenol	44,0	33,6	27,0	22,4
2-ethyl-6-methylphenol	14,6	18,4	22,0	23,6
2-methyl-4-ethylphenol	12,0	20,6	26,4	28,6
2-methyl-3-ethylphenol	-	-	-	0,4
2-methyl-5-ethylphenol	-	-	-	1,4
2-methyl-4,6-diethylphenol	1,0	1,8	2,2	3,0
2-methyl-diethylphenols	-	0,4	0,6	1,0
Substances that boil at high t	0,4	0,8	1,0	1,6
Water	6,0	6,6	7,2	8,0
Gas + loss	1,0	1,2	1,6	4,0
Calculated yields of main reaction products in terms of converted	44,5	40,1	40,6	39,3
2-ethyl-6-ethylphenol	36,6	45,0	48,7	47,7
2-methyl-4-ethylphenol				
2-ethyl-6-ethylphenol	37,1	52,0	61,4	68,0
2-methyl-4-ethylphenol	43,3	52,0	65,3	81,3

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